

bicarbonate solution (5%) and water and dried over Na_2SO_4 (anhydrous). Removal of the solvent yielded the tetrazole (4) which was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol (1 : 5), (1.625 g), m.p. 186° (Found: C, 64.1; H, 8.9; N, 11.1. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 64.14; H, 8.97, N, 11.08%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 520 (C=N), 1 465 and 1 380 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ 5.5 (1H, s, C7 α -H), 4.7 (1H, dd, J_{aa} 10, J_{ab} 7 Hz, C5 α -H), 1.23 (C10- CH_3), 0.57 (C13- CH_3), 0.91, 0.8 and 0.67 (other angular methyl protons).

Under similar reaction conditions (using equal amounts of the reactants), the bromo ketones 2 and 3 afforded the tetrazoles 5 and 6, respectively. The tetrazole 5 was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol (1 : 5), (1.728 g), m.p. 191° (Found: C, 60.1; H, 8.1; N, 10.3. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{BrCl}$ requires: C, 60.05; H, 8.12; N, 10.37%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 525 (C=N), 1 465, 1 380 (N=N) and 735 cm^{-1} (CCl); δ 5.5 (1H, C7 α -H), 4.71 (1H, dd, J_{aa} 9, J_{ab} 7 Hz, C5 α -H), 3.87 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 22 Hz, C3 α -H), 1.18 (C10- CH_3), 0.55 (C13- CH_3), 0.9, 0.8 and 0.65 (remaining methyl protons). The tetrazole 6 was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol (1 : 5) (1.637 g), m.p. 204° (Found: C, 61.7; H, 8.4; N, 2.8. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 61.8; H, 8.40; N, 2.84%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 735 (CH_3COO), 1 235, 1 040 (C-O), 1 520 (C=N), 1 465 and 1 370 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ 5.53 (1H, C7 α -H), 4.67-4.9 (2H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 24 Hz, C3 α -H, C5 α -H), 2.08 (3H, s, CH_3COO), 1.2 (C10- CH_3), 0.58 (C13- CH_3), 0.9, 0.81 and 0.68 (other methyl protons).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. S. Ahmad, and Prof. S. M. Osman, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities. Financial assistance from U.G.C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

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Synthesis and Pharmacological Activity of 1-Benzamide-2-phenyl-4- benzylideneimidazoline-5-one

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Manuscript received 8 October 1987, revised 19 January 1988,
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THE benzylidene imidazolinones are biologically active¹. Interaction of amine with 2-aryl-4-arylidene-2-oxazolin-5-one, under the influence of acetic acid and sodium acetate, yields the corresponding imidazolin-5-ones². Benzocaine and its derivatives are reported as antitubercular³ and bacteriocidal⁴.

Thiosemicarbazone and related compounds of vanillin have been screened against bacteria and fungi substitution with NO_2 or Br seemed to enhance the activity⁵. The structure modification with pharmacologically active grouping have shown excellent results in pharmacology. The title compounds were prepared according to Scheme 1.

R = Different aromatic moieties.

Scheme 1

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF IMIDAZOLIN-5-ONE DERIVATIVES*

R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Interpretation zone of inhibition ($\mu\text{g}/\text{disk}$)**		M. Antituberculosis activity***	
			<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
H	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$	162	-	+	+	-
2-OH	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	150	-	+	+	+
3-OH	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	144	-	-	+	+
4-OH	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	136	+	-	+	+
5-Br, 2-OH	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_5$	135	+	-	-	-
3,5-(Br) ₂ , 2-OH	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_6\text{Br}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	145	+	-	+	-
2,4-(OH) ₂	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	139	+	+	+	+
4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	118	-	-	+	+
5-Br, 4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_6$	117	+	-	+	-
4-OH, 5-I, 3-OCH ₃	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{IN}_2\text{O}_6$	134	-	-	+	+
3-OCH ₃	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	139	+	-	+	+
4-OCH ₃	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	85	+	-	-	+
3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	110	+	-	+	+
5-Br, 3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_6$	128	-	-	+	+
3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_7$	74	-	-	+	+
3,4-(O-CH ₃ , -O)	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	108	+	+	+	+
4-OH ₂	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$	124	-	-	+	+
2-Cl	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_4$	138	-	-	+	+
4-Cl	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_4$	169	+	++	-	-
3-NO ₂	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	95	+	+	+	+
4-NO ₂	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	114	+	++	+	-

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses.

Growth inhibition zone diameter: (+) = ≤ 20 , (++) = > 20 mm. *(+)=No inhibition, (-)=inhibition.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structure of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analyses, counter synthesis, m.m.p. and ir spectral data.

2-Phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)oxazololin-5-one (1): Vanillin (1 mol), hippuric acid (1 mol), acetic anhydride (285 ml) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 mol) were heated to liquification and refluxed for 2 h. Ethanol (200 ml) was then slowly added to the contents and were kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with two portions of ice-cold ethanol and two portions of boiling water and crystallised from absolute ethanol.

1-(4'-Aminobenzamido)-2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)imidazololin-5-one (2): A mixture of 1 (0.6 mol) and 4-aminobenzoylhydrazine (0.6 mol) in pyridine (100 ml) was heated under reflux for 8 h. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The product was diluted with acidified water and was allowed to stand for 4 h at room temperature. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

1-[4'-(Benzylideneamino)benzamido]-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)-2-phenylimidazololin-5-one (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and washed with petroleum ether and

ether and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1); ν_{max} 1 650 (C=O), 1 460 (C=N), 1 280 (C-N), 1 350 (ArN), 850 (*p*-disubstituted-benzene ring), 3 280 cm^{-1} (NH), 1 700 (C=C), 720 (monosubstituted phenyl ring) and 760, 1 040 and 1 130 cm^{-1} (imidazole ring system).

Pharmacological screening: 1-[4'-(Benzylideneamino)benzamido]-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)-2-phenylimidazololin-5-ones were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, and antitubercular activity against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Among all the imidazololin-5-one derivatives only eleven compounds were active against *S. aureus* and only seven compounds were active against *E. coli* at the given concentration. Same compounds were screened for antitubercular activity—six compounds were found active at higher and three at lower concentrations (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University for providing Junior Research Fellowships to two of them (K.N.B.) and (A.M.D.) and to Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh, for pharmacological screening.

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Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded in a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, m.m.p. and ir spectra.

The thiazoles⁶ and the benzthiazoles⁴ were prepared by the reported methods.

2-Imidazolidine thione (1): To a mixture of ethylenediamine (2.0 mol), rectified spirit (300 ml) and water (300 ml), carbon disulphide (2 mol) was added dropwise with occasional shaking for 2 h and refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. Concentrated HCl (15 ml) was then added and further refluxed for 9–10 h. The resulting solid on cooling was filtered, washed with cold acetone (60–80 ml) and crystallised from ethanol.

2-Methylthio-4,5-dihydroimidazole (2): To 1 (1.5 ml) in requisite quantity of 2 N NaOH, dimethyl sulphate (1.5 ml) was added dropwise maintaining the temperature at 40–50° and stirred for 1 h. The contents were then cooled and extracted with ether. Ether solution was dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate) for 8 h and the excess solvent was distilled off. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol.

2-(Benzthiazol-2'-ylamino)-4,5-dihydroimidazole (3): 2 (0.01 mol) and 2-amino benzthiazole (0.01 mol) were refluxed in rectified spirit (50 ml) for 4 h. The contents were then cooled and filtered and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1), ν_{\max} ; 1 440 (C=N), 1 270 (C-N), 700 (C-S), 3 280 (=NH), 400, 650, 810, 885 and 1 100 cm^{-1} (imidazole ring system).

Biological activity: 2-(Substituted-thiazol/benzthiazolyl-amino)-4,5-dihydroimidazoles were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and antitubercular activity against H₃₇R₇ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Studies on Synthesis of 2-(Substituted-thiazolyl/benzthiazolyl-amino)-4,5-dihydroimidazoles

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Manuscript received 12 October 1987, revised 19 January 1988,
accepted 19 February 1988

THE biological activities¹ of condensed heterocycles containing pyridine, pyrimidine, thiazole and imidazole rings, led us to synthesise some imidazole derivatives containing thiazoles and benzthiazoles as substituents. Substituted-benzthiazoles are also biologically active².

The compounds were prepared according to Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF THE IMIDAZOLES (3)*

Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial activity**		Antitubercular activity***	
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	135	68.80	—	—	+	—
6-Cl-Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₉ ClN ₄ S	190	67.32	+	—	+	+
6-OCH ₃ -Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS	120	66.53	+	—	+	+
6-Br-Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₉ BrN ₄ S	195	60.60	+	+	+	+
6-(SO ₂ NH ₂)-Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	289	65.65	+	—	+	—
4-(C ₆ H ₅)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	115	67.34	—	—	+	+
4-(C ₆ H ₄ Cl)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₄ S	150	62.61	—	+	+	+
4-(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S	165	68.96	—	—	+	—
4-(C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS	158	69.09	+	—	+	+
4-(C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ S	145	68.70	+	—	—	—

*Elementary analyses found satisfactory.

(+)=Inhibition, (—)=no inhibition. *(+)=No inhibition, (—)=inhibition.